

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

AKHMADJONOV MUKHAMMADYUSUF

ACADEMIC LYCEUM UNDER THE UNIVERSITY OF WORLD ECONOMY AND DIPLOMACY

+99893 661 21 11

www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10457329

ANNOTATION: The most important general-purpose technology of our time is artificial intelligence, specifically machine learning (ML) - that is, the ability of a machine to continue to improve its performance without humans having to explain exactly how to do it. In the past few years, machine learning has become much more efficient and widespread. Now we can create systems that learn to perform tasks independently

Keywords: technology, innovation, human, science, method, in search of artificial intelligence, better outcomes , airlines , self-learning maintenance.

INTRODUCTION

The term artificial intelligence was coined in 1955 by Dartmouth mathematics professor John McCarthy, who organized a landmark conference on the subject the following year. Since then, perhaps in part because of its impressive name, the field has had more than its fair share of fanciful claims and promises. In 1957, economist Herbert Simon predicted that computers would beat humans at chess within 10 years. In 1967, cognitive scientist Marvin Minsky said, "Once the original has passed, the problem of creating 'artificial intelligence' will be largely solved." Dramatic claims of future progress are understandably met with some degree of skepticism.

MAIN PART

Artificial intelligence and machine learning come in many flavors, but most of the successes of recent years fall into one category: supervised learning systems, in which a machine is taught many times to correctly answer a given problem. gave examples. This process almost always involves a mapping from a set of inputs X to a set of outputs Y . For example, inputs can be pictures of different animals, and correct outputs can be labels for those animals: dog, cat, horse. . Inputs can also be waveforms of a voice recording, and outputs can be words: "yes", "no", "hello", "goodbye". (See the exhibit "Supervised Learning Systems.") Successful systems often use training data sets with thousands or even millions of examples, each labeled with a correct answer. The system can then be relaxed to view new instances. If the training went well, the system will predict the answers with high accuracy.

Does this mean that artificial intelligence and machine learning can't do anything? Perception and perception cover a lot of territory—from driving a car to forecasting sales to deciding who to hire or advertise. We believe that artificial intelligence will soon reach superhuman levels of efficiency in most or all of these areas. So what can't AI and ML do?

We sometimes hear: "Artificial intelligence will never be good at evaluating emotional, cunning, cunning, inconsistent people - it is too harsh and personal for that." We disagree. ML systems like Affectiva are already at or above human level when it comes to detecting a person's emotional state based on tone of voice or facial expression.

Other systems allow even the world's best poker players to bluff enough to beat them in a surprisingly complex game of Heads-up No-Limit Texas Hold'em. Reading people correctly is a delicate task, but not magical. This requires insight and perception – exactly the areas where ML is currently strong and is always growing stronger.

We believe that artificial intelligence, especially machine learning, is the most important general purpose technology of our time. The impact of these innovations on business and the economy is evident not only in their direct contributions, but also in their ability to enable and inspire complementary innovations. New product and process vision systems, speech recognition, intelligent problem solving and many other possibilities are being created.

The term “artificial intelligence” was coined more than 60 years ago, but only recently have we begun to realize all the benefits of AI, machine learning and deep learning in our everyday lives.

Most of us already use smart machines that learn, recognize voices, make decisions, solve problems and make recommendations on everything from the routes we drive, to the movies we watch, to the clothes we buy.

We have smartphones in our pockets, intelligent personal assistants on our countertops, robots in our factories and autonomous vehicles on our highways. And that’s just for starters.

Artificial intelligence, Deep Learning / Machine Learning Systems are having a major impact on the aerospace industry, too. With the technologies mentioned above, flying is becoming safer, more comfortable, more predictive and outcome based. Airlines improve schedule performance, use less fuel and create a better passenger experience. Airports are more efficient and easier for travelers to navigate. Ground crews turn flights around faster and dispatch operations are getting more efficient and autonomy based. Airlines are able to use the learning systems to derive better segment strategies and charge according to the relevance and value. And aircraft maintenance is easier, faster, prescriptive and more precise.

All this – and much more – is possible because aerospace is such a data-rich ecosystem. With recent advancements in connectivity, data analytics and the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), we can use the vast amounts of data available from disparate systems on and off the aircraft to drive outcomes that impact the operational efficiency, mission effectiveness and profitability of all kinds of operators. AI, Machine Learning and Deep Learning are the engines that connects brains throughout the ecosystem. Not to leave out manufacturing, the digital—physical—digital loop bound by digital threads is taking Industry 4.0 to an altogether different level by creating self-learning networks capable of bringing in an astounding level of autonomy and decision making without humans in the loop.

Let’s look at a few areas in the airline world which are impacted very positively and deeply. For example, artificial intelligence is getting at the heart of maintenance solutions, which provides maintenance techs with an unprecedented level of information and insights about the performance and health of onboard aircraft systems. Airline operators have experienced a 35 percent reduction in operational disruptions thanks to artificial intelligence and deep learning infusion.

With AI and Deep Learning, the intelligent and self-learning maintenance system has the capability to monitors onboard systems, model nominal behavior, detect aberrations and analyzes data and patterns from past events to predict that a fault will occur days in advance. Then, the system provides prescriptive insights to recommend corrective actions and alert the supply chain to order the right parts and materials.

Airlines spend a lot on fuel and what a treat would it be to use modern technologies to bring down this significant cost. AI and Deep Learning Models can crunch data from hundreds of available sources and make recommendations that can reduce fuel consumption and hence

operation cost. Even a 1-3 percent saving amounts to tens-of-millions of dollars in annual savings for some carriers. And all this is being made possible by the ingress of intelligent and self-learning models. It is helping airlines uncover novel fuel savings opportunities that are tailored for their specific fleet and operating profile, covering critical factors such as weight, engine utilization and fuel planning.

Another great case where we see lot of benefit is streamlining and make ground operations more efficient and automated. Connectivity, data analytics expertise and modelling the success criteria help airlines reduce block time by improving the ground-handling process, which can have a significant impact on the carrier's on-time performance. It enables airlines and ground service providers reduce turn-around time by as much as 13 – 15 percent, increasing the number of flights that takeoff on time, a key airline metric and passenger-satisfaction factor.

The setup gives the operations team real-time insight into the status, location and activity of all aircraft and ground equipment, creating the first truly “connected ramp.

” Ground vehicles transmit data to the enabling solution, allowing users to monitor vehicle use, improve services and enhance safety.

There are many other examples of how connected aerospace, AI and advanced data analytics are helping to reinvent the entire air transportation system by smashing down the data silos of the past and bringing the power of connected to deliver better outcomes for everyone in the aerospace ecosystem.

CONCLUSION

In the case of our article, the model's highest-scoring sentence is the one beginning “The most important general-purpose technology of our era is artificial intelligence,” which is also arguably the article's thesis. In that sense, the extractive summarizer did well.

References:

1. Sweeney, Y. 2020. “Tracking the Debate on COVID-19 Surveillance Tools,” *Nature Machine Intelligence* (2:6), pp. 301-304.
2. Tegmark, M. 2017. *Life 3.0: Being Human in the Age of Artificial Intelligence*, New York: Alfred A. Knopf
3. Weber, M. 2018. *Economy and Society: An Outline of Interpretive Sociology*, G. Roth and C. Wittich (eds.), Berkeley, CA: University of California Press.
4. Zuboff, S. 2018. In *The Age Of The Smart Machine: The Future of Work and Power*, New York: Basic Books.
5. Aerospace.honeywell.com "In search of Artificial intelligence".